

Spontaneous Hepatocellular Carcinoma in a Golden Hamster: A Rare Case with Ultrasonographic Detection and Cytopathological Confirmation

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Abstract: Hepatocellular carcinoma is a malignant neoplasm originating from hepatocytes. Although this neoplastic disease occurs spontaneously in various animal species, it is particularly well documented in rodent models used in hepatocarcinogenesis research. Spontaneous occurrence of hepatocellular carcinoma in hamsters is extremely rare and most published cases occur under experimental carcinogenic conditions. Naturally occurring hepatocellular carcinoma in domestic hamsters is rare and its clinical and pathologic features are poorly described in the veterinary literature. In this case report, we present a rare case of spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma in 2-year-old an intact female golden hamster and emphasize the diagnostic findings based on ultrasonographic evaluation and cytopathologic confirmation. Given the rarity of spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma in hamsters, each documented case adds meaningful data to the understanding of the clinical presentation, diagnostic approach and pathologic features in this species. In addition, the scientific significance of this case report is the inclusion of abdominal ultrasonographic features in a hamster with pathologically confirmed spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma.

Keywords: Cytopathological, golden hamster, hepatocellular carcinoma, ultrasonography

Bir Golden Hamsterda Spontan Hepatoselüler Karsinom: Ultrasonografik Tespit ve Sitopatolojik Doğrulama ile Nadir Bir Olgu

Özet: Hepatoselüler karsinom, hepatositlerden kaynaklanan malign bir neoplazmdır. Bu neoplastik hastalık çeşitli hayvan türlerinde spontan olarak ortaya çıksa da özellikle hepatokarsinogenez araştırmalarında kullanılan kemirgen modellerinde iyi huylu olarak bildirilmektedir. Hamsterlarda hepatoselüler karsinomun kendiliğinden oluşması son derece nadirdir ve yayınlanan vakaların çoğu

deneyisel karsinojenik koşullar altında meydana gelir. Evcil hamsterlarda doğal olarak ortaya çıkan hepatoselüler karsinom nadirdir. Klinik ve patolojik özellikleri veteriner literatüründe yeterince tanımlanmamıştır. Bu olgu sunumunda, 2 yaşında sağlam bir dişi golden hamsterda nadir görülen spontan hepatoselüler karsinom olgusu sunulmakta ve ultrasonografik değerlendirme ve sitopatolojik doğrulamaya dayanan tanısal bulgular vurgulanmaktadır. Hamsterlarda spontan hepatoselüler karsinomun nadir görülmesi nedeniyle, belgelenen her vaka bu türdeki klinik tablo, tanısal yaklaşım ve patolojik özelliklerin anlaşılmasına anlamlı veriler katacağı, ayrıca patolojik olarak doğrulanmış spontan hepatoselüler karsinomlu bir hamsterde abdominal ultrasonografik özelliklerin dahil edilmesinin literatür bilgiye katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Altın hamster, hepatoselüler karsinom, sitopatolojik, ultrasonografi

INTRODUCTION

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a malignant neoplasm originating from hepatocytes and is well-documented in various animal species, particularly in rodent models used for hepatocarcinogenesis research (Bakiri and Wagner, 2013, Erdoğan, 2024). In laboratory animals such as rats and mice, HCC may occur spontaneously or be induced chemically by agents such as diethylnitrosamine, aflatoxin B1, or streptozotocin (Sigurðarson, 2023). However, spontaneous occurrence of HCC in hamsters is exceedingly rare, with most published cases arising under experimental carcinogenic conditions (Cheleuitte-Nieves et al., 2021). The clinical and pathological features of naturally occurring HCC in pet hamsters remain poorly characterized in veterinary literature.

To the best of our knowledge, reports of spontaneous HCC in pet hamsters, particularly in golden hamsters (*Mesocricetus auratus*), are extremely limited. This case report presents a rare instance of spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma in 2-year-old an intact female golden hamster, emphasizing diagnostic findings based on ultrasonographic evaluation and cytopathological confirmation.

CASE PRESENTATION

2-year-old, nulliparous, an intact female golden hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*) was presented with a two-week history of progressive abdominal distension and subcutaneous discoloration in the lower abdominal region. The animal had not been previously bred and had no significant prior medical history. Physical examination revealed generalized abdominal enlargement without palpable discrete masses. No abnormalities were detected in the mammary chain or external genitalia.

Abdominal ultrasonographic examination revealed the presence of free anechoic fluid in the abdominal cavity, consistent with ascites (Figure 1). The uterus appeared within normal anatomical limits, with no anechoic or cystic abnormalities noted.

Figure 1. Abdominal ultrasonographic examination shows the presence of free anechoic fluid in the abdominal cavity consistent with ascites. Note that the bowel loop is floating due to the fluid

Both kidneys were normal in size and echotexture; however, the right kidney exhibited mild caudal displacement. The urinary bladder was intact and maintained normal wall integrity and volume.

Liver parenchyma displayed irregular margins, heterogeneous echogenicity, and poor visualization of lobar architecture (Figure 2). A fine-needle aspirate (FNA) was obtained from the hepatic region under ultrasound guidance, and abdominal fluid was sampled via abdominocentesis. The fluid was grossly hemorrhagic and suggestive of hemoabdomen.

Figure 2. The liver parenchyma had irregular margins, heterogeneous echogenicity and poor visualization of the lobar structure. Note the hyperechogenic appearance of the gallbladder wall

Cytopathological evaluation of the hepatic aspirate revealed cohesive clusters of variably sized hepatocytes, marked anisocytosis and anisokaryosis, and evidence of megalocytosis. The

hepatocyte nuclei were round, centrally located or eccentrically displaced, with coarse chromatin and multiple indistinct nucleoli. Cytoplasm appeared vacuolated and basophilic. Additionally, degenerate malignant hepatocytes were identified within the hemorrhagic abdominal effusion.

Based on the cytologic features and clinical findings, a diagnosis of spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma was established. Unfortunately, the patient died a few days following diagnosis, and necropsy could not be performed as per the owner's decision.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma is an uncommon diagnosis in companion rodents, particularly in golden hamsters (Dekant et al., 2021). Most hepatic tumors reported in this species have been experimentally induced through chemical carcinogens or hormonal modulation. The occurrence of HCC in this patient without any known exposure to hepatotoxins or prior hormonal manipulation underscores the rarity and clinical significance of the case (Yamada et al., 2021).

Ultrasonographic findings in this case loss of normal hepatic architecture, irregular parenchymal echogenicity, and concurrent ascites were instrumental in prompting further diagnostic intervention. Although ultrasound has limitations in detecting small hepatic nodules in small mammals, the presence of ascites and poorly visualized liver borders should raise suspicion for intra-abdominal neoplasia (Wajid, 2018). Notably, the uterus and urinary system were sonographically normal, reducing the likelihood of reproductive or urinary etiologies contributing to abdominal enlargement.

Cytological evaluation played a critical role in the definitive diagnosis, revealing hallmark features of hepatic malignancy such as cellular pleomorphism, megalocytosis, and disorganized hepatocellular clusters (Zhou et al., 2020). The identification of malignant hepatocytes in the abdominal fluid further supported the diagnosis and indicated advanced disease with likely abdominal dissemination.

This case contributes to the limited body of literature on naturally occurring HCC in hamsters and highlights the value of integrating ultrasonographic assessment with cytopathology for the diagnosis of internal neoplasia in exotic small mammals. While necropsy would have provided further insight into metastatic spread and tumor burden, the cytological and imaging findings were sufficient to reach a definitive diagnosis.

This case report has some limitations. First, a full necropsy could not be performed due to the owner's refusal, which restricted comprehensive evaluation of metastatic spread or potential primary tumor burden in other organs. Second, the diagnosis was based solely on ultrasonographic and cytological analysis without histopathological confirmation from a tissue biopsy or post-mortem specimen. Although cytological features were consistent with hepatocellular carcinoma, a definitive diagnosis via histopathology would have strengthened the findings.

Given the rarity of spontaneous hepatocellular carcinoma in hamsters, each documented case adds meaningful data to the understanding of its clinical presentation, diagnostic approach, and pathological characteristics in this species.

Contributions: MÖ contributed to the conception and design of the study. The MÖ and ÇE carried out the material preparation and data collection. MÖ and ÇE contributed to the writing and editing of the final draft of the manuscript. The manuscript was read by MÖ and ÇE and approved by both authors.

Conflict of Interest Statement: There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

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